

CODE-SWITCHING AND INTERFERENCE IN DEVELOPING ADVANCED LEVEL STUDENTS' STRATEGIC COMPETENCE IN ORAL LANGUAGE

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Annotation

This article explores the role of code-switching and interference in the development of advanced level students' strategic competence in oral language. Communication strategies are essential in second language acquisition and are used to compensate for gaps in knowledge or to express meaning in a second language. Code-switching and interference can impact the use of communication strategies and the development of strategic competence. The article provides examples of code-switching and interference in the oral communication of advanced level students and discusses the implications for language teaching and learning.

Key words: Interference, strategic competence, oral interaction, innovative methods, strategies.

Аннотация

В этой статье исследуется роль интерференции в развитие стратегической компетенции учащихся продвинутого уровня в устной речи. Стратегии общения необходимы для овладения вторым языком и используются для компенсации пробелов в знаниях или для выражения смысла на втором языке. Виды интерференции могут повлиять на использование коммуникативных стратегий и развитие стратегической компетентности. В статье приводятся примеры интерференции в устную коммуникацию учащихся продвинутого уровня и обсуждаются последствия для преподавания и изучения языка.

Ключевые слова: Интерференция, стратегическая компетенция, речевое взаимодействие, инновационные методы, стратегии.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqola talabalarning og'zaki tilda strategik kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishda interferensiya va uning turlarini ko'rib chiqdik. Muloqot strategiyalari chet tilni o'zlashtirishda muhim ahamiyatga ega va bilimlardagi

bo'shliqlarni qoplash yoki ikkinchi tilda ma'noni ifodalash uchun ishlatiladi. Interferensiya hodisasi aloqa strategiyalaridan foydalanishga va strategik kompetensiyani rivojlantirishga ta'sir qilishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: Interferensiya, strategik kompetensiya, og'zaki o'zaro ta'sir, innovatsion usullar, strategiyalar.

Code-switching is a common phenomenon in multilingual communities, and it can occur for various reasons, such as to express identity, to fill gaps in vocabulary or grammar, or to convey meaning more effectively. Here are the features of code-switching that appear in using strategic competence in oral interaction:

Awareness of language and cultural norms: Speakers who possess strategic competence in code switching are aware of the different linguistic and cultural norms associated with each language or language variety they use, and they are able to switch between them appropriately.

Flexibility in language use: Speakers with strategic competence in code switching are flexible in their language use and can adapt their language to suit different communicative contexts and interlocutors.

Control over code switching: Speakers with strategic competence in code switching are able to control when and how they switch between languages or language varieties in order to achieve their communicative goals.

Metalinguistic awareness: Speakers with strategic competence in code switching possess a metalinguistic awareness of the different linguistic features of each language or language variety they use, and are able to use this knowledge to facilitate their code switching [1,42].

However, the use of code-switching and interference can impact the use of communication strategies and the development of strategic competence. Interference can occur when the structures, sounds, or vocabulary of one language are transferred to another language, resulting in errors or misunderstandings. In the context of language learning, code-switching and interference can hinder the development of strategic competence, which is essential for effective communication in a second language [2, 100].

Advanced level students who are proficient in both their first language and second language may experience code-switching and interference in their oral communication. For example, a student may code-switch to their first language when they are unable to express a complex concept or idea in the second language. This can hinder the development of strategic competence, as

the student may not be developing their ability to use communication strategies effectively in the second language.

Interference can also occur when the structures, sounds, or vocabulary of the first language are transferred to the second language. For example, a student may use the intonation patterns of their first language when speaking in the second language, which can result in misunderstandings or confusion. This can also hinder the development of strategic competence, as the student may not be aware of the impact of their first language on their use of the second language [3, 251].

Phonological interference: Bilingual speakers who are aware of their phonological deficits in the second language may use strategies such as mimicry, where they try to imitate the pronunciation of native speakers, or accommodation, where they modify their pronunciation to match the speech of their interlocutors.

Morphological interference: Bilingual speakers who are aware of their morphological deficits in the second language may use strategies such as circumlocution, where they use multiple words to express a concept that would be expressed with a single word in the second language, or simplification, where they use simpler grammatical structures to convey their message.

Syntactic interference: Bilingual speakers who are aware of their syntactic deficits in the second language may use strategies such as restructuring, where they modify the sentence structure to make it more grammatically correct, or simplification, where they use shorter and simpler sentences to convey their message.

Semantic interference: Bilingual speakers who are aware of their semantic deficits in the second language may use strategies such as circumlocution, where they use multiple words to express a concept that would be expressed with a single word in the second language, or clarification, where they ask for clarification or provide additional information to make their message clearer.

Pragmatic interference: Bilingual speakers who are aware of their pragmatic deficits in the second language may use strategies such as clarification, where they ask for clarification or provide additional information to ensure that their message is understood, or adaptation, where they modify their communication style to match the cultural norms of their interlocutors [4,787].

Here are some suggested methods for teachers to help students overcome problems with code switching and interference and develop strategic competence in oral communication:

Explicitly teach communication strategies: Teachers can explicitly teach communication strategies to help students compensate for gaps in knowledge or vocabulary and maintain effective communication. They can model the use of these strategies in class and provide opportunities for students to practice using them.

Encourage the use of the target language: Teachers can encourage students to use the target language as much as possible in class, even if they make mistakes or need to use communication strategies to compensate for gaps in their knowledge. This helps students develop confidence and fluency in the target language.

Provide corrective feedback: Teachers can provide corrective feedback to students when they make errors or use inappropriate language. This feedback should be constructive and focused on helping students improve their language use, rather than simply pointing out mistakes [5,190].

Create a supportive classroom environment: Teachers can create a supportive classroom environment where students feel comfortable taking risks and making mistakes. This can be achieved by fostering a sense of community in the classroom, providing opportunities for collaboration and peer support, and celebrating students' successes.

Use authentic materials: Teachers can use authentic materials, such as videos, podcasts, and news articles, to expose students to real-life language use and help them develop their listening and speaking skills. These materials can also be used to teach students about cultural differences and help them develop intercultural competence.

By implementing these methods, teachers can help students overcome problems with code switching and interference and develop strategic competence in oral communication [6, 35-40].

Provide opportunities for meaningful communication: Teachers can provide opportunities for students to engage in meaningful communication, such as discussions, debates, and presentations. This helps students develop their critical thinking, problem-solving, and communication skills.

Scaffold language use: Teachers can scaffold students' language use by providing support and guidance when needed. This can include providing vocabulary lists, sentence frames, and model language.

Incorporate technology: Teachers can incorporate technology, such as video conferencing and language learning apps, to provide students with opportunities to practice their oral communication skills outside of the

classroom. This can help students develop their confidence and fluency in the target language.

Address individual needs: Teachers can address individual students' needs by providing differentiated instruction and support. This can include providing extra practice or one-on-one tutoring for students who need it.

Foster metacognitive awareness: Teachers can foster metacognitive awareness by helping students reflect on their language learning and communication strategies. This can help students develop self-awareness, self-regulation, and self-efficacy in their language learning [7, 95].

In conclusion, communication strategies are an important component of oral language development and play a crucial role in compensating for gaps in knowledge or vocabulary. Research has shown that explicit instruction in communication strategies can improve students' communication skills and confidence in using the target language, and that technology can be a useful tool in teaching communication strategies. Additionally, there is a growing interest in the use of task-based language teaching to promote the use of communication strategies in the classroom.

Although code-switching and interference can be challenging for students, teachers can use a variety of strategies to help students develop strategic competence in oral communication, such as explicitly teaching communication strategies, providing opportunities for practice and feedback, and promoting learner autonomy. By implementing these methods, teachers can support their students in becoming effective communicators in both their first and second languages.

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